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Develop High Temperature – High Performance Glass Fibre/PAEK Thermoplastic Prepregs

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Outline of presentation

- **Introduction**
- **Objectives**
- **Methodology and Approach**
- **Outcome and Results**
- **Future work**

Fibre-Reinforced Composites

- 50% lighter than steel, 30% lighter than aluminum and remarkably strong.
- Composites have many applications in aerospace industry.

PRIMARY STRUCTURES

50%
Advanced
Composites

Sheldon Wilkinson

Prepregs

- “Pre-impregnated” reinforcing fabric, which has been impregnated with a resin system.
- Prepreg is ready to lay into the mold without the addition of any more resin.
- Advantages:
 - ✓ Convenience of using prepreg
 - ✓ Minimum flaws in the required ratio of each component
 - ✓ A stronger, more durable and homogenous composite
 - ✓ Far less waste on our hand

Advantages of thermoplastics

- Soften on heating and pressure, and thus easy to repair
- High strains to failure
- Indefinite shelf life
- Can be reprocessed
- Not tacky and easy to handle
- Short cure cycles
- Higher fabrication temperature and viscosities have made it difficult to process
- Excellent solvent resistance

PAEK (Poly Aryl Ether Ketone)

- PAEK polymers are semi-crystalline thermoplastics. Examples are; PEEK and PEKK.

- ✓ Glass transition (T_g) of 149 to 162°C
- ✓ Maintain properties up to T_g
- ✓ High toughness
- ✓ High damage tolerance
- ✓ Excellent fire retardancy
- ✓ Low flame and smoke
- ✓ High chemical resistance

- Properties of PAEK resin makes it a suitable choice for composites in fuselage production.

Tasks and Challenges

- Develop high temperature – high performance prepreg materials to withstand temperatures between -65 °C and +200°C
- Design and manufacture in-house production rig with uniform fibre spread, effective resin impregnation and controlled fibre volume content
- Incorporating various nano-materials in the thermoplastic resin with studies on fire resistance, mechanical and interfacial properties

Resin Impregnation (Slurry Prepreging)

The challenge is to impregnate glass fibers with thermoplastic powder

Slurry Processing: The PEKK powder is suspended in a liquid carrier. The dispersion is applied to fibrous textile to distribute the resin over the fibres.

Fine PEKK Powder

Woven fabric prepreg line

Prepreg production line using woven glass tape.

(a)

Tape haul off

(b)

Resin
impregnation

(c)

Metering
rollers

(d)

Heat Melting

(e)

Tape Take Up

Unidirectional (UD) Fabric Prepreg line

Drum winding prepreg line concept.

Prepregs produced

S-2 Glass Fibre

- ✓ Effective resin impregnation
- ✓ Uniform fibre spread
- ✓ Uniform resin content
- ✓ Low thickness variation
- ✓ Low areal weight variation
- ✓ Control overall fibre and resin ratio
- ✓ Control overall thickness

Carbon Fibre

Laminating

Typical Cure Cycle for Press Molding

Cross-section Micrographs

In-house production

- ✓ Full resin impregnation
- ✓ Very low void content
- ✓ Minimum resin reach area
- ✓ Excellent dispersion of fibre

TenCate Cetex TC1200

Tensile properties

Sample description	S2-PAEK-10%-4ply-UD-10b-350c-20m
Reinforcing fibre	S2 Glass
Polymer	Victrex PAEK
Resin percentage (%)	10
Number of plies	4
Stacking sequence	UD
Processing pressure (bar)	10
Processing temperature (°C)	350
Processing time (min)	20

	Tensile strength [MPa]	Failure strain [%]	Modulus (Chord 0.1 % - 0.3 %) [GPa]	Modulus (Chord 0.2 % - 0.4 %) [GPa]	Modulus (Chord 0.3 % - 0.5 %) [GPa]	Width [mm]	Thickness [mm]	Area [mm ²]
1	1690	2.57	69.3	66.3	64.6	10.10	0.54	5.45
2	1710	2.81	71.4	68.9	67.4	10.10	0.54	5.45
3	1640	3.86	62.2	60.5	60.1	10.05	0.54	5.43
4	1690	2.35	68.7	68.7	68.4	10.10	0.54	5.45
5	1760	2.51	62.6	61.8	61.3	10.12	0.53	5.36
Mean	1700	2.82	66.8	65.3	64.4	10.09	0.54	5.43
Standard deviation	46.0	0.604	4.16	3.90	3.62	0.03	0.00	0.04
Coefficient of variation	2.71	21.4	6.22	5.97	5.62	0.26	0.83	0.72

Tensile properties

30% resin: 900 MPa strength, 3.2% failure strain and 31 GPa Modulus

20% resin: 1350 MPa strength, 3.3% failure strain and 47 GPa Modulus

10% resin: 1550 MPa strength, 2.8% failure strain and 62 GPa Modulus

Merits

- Novel and patent pending method
- Very cost effective
- Small in size
- Great for lab scale research
- Control over spread and fibre volume.
- Full impregnation of fibre filaments.
- Easy addition of Nano-additives.

Limits

- Slight thickness variation due to fibre overlap
- No continuous production
- Prepreg size limit

Future works

- Test rig is constantly being optimized and upgraded.
- The composite developed will be tested at high temperatures up to 300 °C.
- Optical micrographs will be used to determine the optimum, fibre/resin content.
- Tensile and impact tests in room and elevated temperatures to characterize mechanical properties.
- Optional particles such as Graphene, Carbon Nano Tube (CNT) and Nano-Clay will be added to matrix to enhance material properties.

Thank you for your attention

Any questions?